

THE STATE OF TECHNICAL DATA ON THE HYDRODYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MOORED ARRAY COMPONENTS

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Abstract

A survey is presented of the available hydrodynamic data on components of suspended-array mooring systems. The data are used by the system designer in calculating the forces and motions induced in the system by the dynamic ocean environment. The components include a variety of shapes of packages which contain oceanographic sensors and other moored array components. The data include hydrodynamic load coefficients, added mass and damping coefficients, and strumming effects which result from surface waves and subsurface currents. The various components are catalogued according to types and shapes of components. Types include sensor and array elements, mooring lines, and buoys. The quality and quantity of data are assessed. Suggestions are given for research to improve the quality and quantity of certain data.

1. Introduction

Various organizations involved in ocean research develop suspended array systems for such applications as the measurement of environmental parameters, weather prediction, and the tracking of military and commercial shipping. Designers of the moorings for these systems require a knowledge of the hydrodynamic environment, including surface wave spectra and subsurface currents to be expected at the site of interest. They also need to know the responses of the system's components. When the environment is known many of these responses may be determined from the hydrodynamic characteristics of the various components. This paper explores the state of technical data on the hydrodynamic characteristics of oceanographic sensors and mooring components and indicates their use in determining the responses of such systems.

In an investigation for the Naval Facilities Engineering Command, the published and unpublished literature was searched to establish the present level of technical knowledge of experimental and analytical procedures and of data on the hydrodynamics of components of moored arrays and

similar systems. Data from selected sources were extracted and arranged according to component shape and major grouping of hydrodynamic characteristics, including hydrodynamic load coefficients, added mass and damping coefficients, strumming, and responses in waves.

As to the state of the data, complete data were found for components with simple geometric shapes, such as cylinders and spheres. However, data for more complex shapes were incomplete. In the sections which follow, the quality and quantity of data are assessed. Suggestions are given for research to improve the quality and quantity of certain data.

2. Hydrodynamic Parameters

In the ocean environment, moored array components are acted upon by different forces, including gravity, tensions from the mooring lines, hydrostatic forces, and steady and unsteady hydrodynamic forces. All the forces affect the responses of moored array components to the environment. This paper concentrates on the hydrodynamic forces.

As discussed by Morgan (Reference 1), steady hydrodynamic forces induced by a steady current on a body may include both friction and gravity components and are relatable to the inertia of the moving fluid by the following Newtonian force coefficients:

$$\text{Drag coefficient } C_D = \frac{D}{(1/2)\rho U^2 A_D}, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Lift coefficient } C_L = \frac{L}{(1/2)\rho U^2 A_L}, \quad \text{and } (2)$$

$$\text{Moment coefficient } C_M = \frac{M}{(1/2)\rho U^2 \ell A_L} \quad (3)$$

where A_D and A_L are the characteristic areas for drag and lift (such as frontal area and planform area), D and L are drag and lift forces, ℓ is a characteristic length of the body, M is pitching moment, U is flow velocity, and ρ is water density. These coefficients typically depend on angle of attack and on the Froude number, $F_n = U/\sqrt{g\ell}$ and Reynolds number, $R_n = U\ell/\nu$ where ν is the kinematic viscosity.

matic viscosity and g is the acceleration due to gravity.

The typical case of a sensor or array component oscillating in pure translation, as shown in Figure 1 may be used to illustrate unsteady forces. In this case, the unsteady forces can be described by an equation of motion of the form:

$$m'\ddot{z} + c\dot{z} + kz = F(t) \quad (4)$$

where c is the damping factor, k is the spring constant provided by the mooring lines, m' is the virtual mass (mass of the body m plus the added mass of water m_a), z is the displacement of the component from an equilibrium position, and the dots represent time derivatives. Similar equations exist for other translational and rotational modes of motion. Added mass and damping data are often presented as functions of amplitude and frequency of motion. Also, spring constants are functions of the configurations in which the components are moored. The above oscillating system has a natural frequency given by:

$$f_o = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m'}} \quad (5)$$

Figure 1 - Cylindrical Component Subject to Typical Flow and Motions

In a steady current, cylinders, spheres and other shapes often are subjected to transverse or lift forces due to vortex shedding at a frequency defined by:

$$f_s = \frac{US_n}{l} \quad (6)$$

where S_n is the Strouhal number, which is a function of Reynolds number. When the frequency f_s approaches f_o , vortex shedding excites the component into resonance. This phenomenon, called strumming, can lead to structural failure or sensor overload.

The wave effects on moored components also must be considered. The motion of the water

particles generated by waves is at its maximum at the surface and diminishes below the surface. When water particles move less than a significant length of the moored component, the effect of waves can be neglected. The relationship between the amplitude of water particle motion in deep water and the surface wave amplitude is shown in the following equation:

$$A(h) = A_o \exp(-\omega^2 h/g) \quad (7)$$

where $A(h)$ and A_o are single amplitudes of the water particle and waves respectively, h is the depth of submergence and ω is the wave frequency in rad/sec.

One empirical formulation of surface wave amplitude is that of Bretschneider, (Reference 2)

$$A_o = \frac{32.4 H_s}{T_s^2 \omega^3} \exp\left(-\frac{525}{T_s^4 \omega^4}\right) \text{ feet} \quad (8)$$

where H_s is the significant wave height in feet and T_s is the average period of the wave in seconds.

It follows from the above discussions that the sources of some hydrodynamic forces on mooring components depend on the depth at which the components are submerged. When a component is on or near the surface, surface waves are the primary source of hydrodynamic loading. When the component is submerged, current is usually the main source of hydrodynamic loading. Changes of water depth also affect hydrodynamic characteristics. When a component is submerged in intermediate or shallow water where the speed of the current is high, the strumming force induced by the shedding or vortices is important. It is not an important factor, however, when the component is deeply submerged and the speed of the current is low.

Thus, the nature of the hydrodynamic characteristics of a mooring system is related to the location of the array and to the depth of submergence of each of its components. The importance of the depth of submergence on the hydrodynamic characteristics of the types of component considered here is indicated in Table 1.

With the above considerations, the designer may use hydrodynamic data summarized below in various mathematical models to predict the performance of a moored system in the ocean environment. Details on various models are given in References 3, 4 and 5.

3. Survey of Data Available

For convenience in the assessment of hydrodynamic data, moored array components may be divided into three general groups according to component shape. The first group contains basic shapes of packages and housings which enclose oceanographic sensors and other subsurface components. A second group contains basic shapes of various mooring lines. A third group contains various shapes of surface and subsurface buoys.

TABLE 1. IMPORTANCE OF VARIOUS HYDRODYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Depth of Submergence	Hydrodynamic Characteristics	Steady Forces (drag, lift)	Added Mass	Damping	Strumming	R _n	F _n	S _n
Great depth of submergence in deep sea where low current exists		A	C	C	C	A	C	C
Intermediate and shallow submergence where higher current exists		A	B	C	A	A	A	A
Shallow submergence and surface where wave effects exist		B	A	A	A	B	A	A

where
 A: Predominant parameter
 B: Important parameter
 C: Nonimportant parameter
 R_n: Reynolds Number; the ratio of inertia to viscous forces
 F_n: Froude Number; the ratio of inertia to gravity forces
 S_n: Strouhal Number; the period parameter of vortex shedding

For the three groups, the availability of the data is summarized in a matrix form in Table 2. The letter symbols indicate whether the available data are ample, adequate, or inadequate for each combination of parameter and type of component. Ample indicates that many sources of data are available to characterize the parameter in question. Adequate indicates that enough sources are available to choose from. Inadequate indicates that either too few sources or no sources are available.

TABLE 2. AVAILABILITY OF HYDRODYNAMIC DATA

Type of Components	Range of Parameters	Flow Forces		Added Mass and Dynamic Responses	
		Normal Axial Moment		Normal Axial Moment	
Packages and Housings	Cylinders	B	C	B	C
	Spheres	A	A	A	A
	Spheroids	A	B	B	B
	Ellipsoids	C	C	B	B
	Other Streamline Shapes	B	A	B	B
Mooring Lines	Rigid Cylinders	A	A	A	A
	Bare Cable	A	A	A	B
	Chain	A	C	C	C
	Cable Fairings:				
	Fringe & Ribbon	B	B	C	C
Streamlined	A	B	C	C	
Other	A	B	C	C	
Buoys		Combined		Combined	
	General Floating Bodies	A		B	
	Specific Surface Buoys	A		A	
	Submerged Buoys	A		B	
	Buoy Appendages	A		C	

A Ample B Adequate C Inadequate * not applicable

Basic Shapes for Packages and Housings

The basic shapes include the following generic shapes: circular cylinders with flat, hemispherical, and conical ends; spheres; oblate and prolate spheroids; and general streamlined shapes such as torpedo shapes.

Of all the shapes considered, the hydrodynamic characteristics of prolate spheroids and torpedo-shaped bodies have been most extensively investigated. Thus, data for these bodies are the most reliable for ocean engineering applications.

The existing data for finite length cylindrical bodies tend to be sketchy and piecemeal. A measure of engineering judgment is recommended in selecting the hydrodynamic data for these components.

However, finite length cylinders are often used to house oceanographic sensors. In a typical situation, as shown in Figure 1 these sensors are subjected to current normal to the cylinder and to mooring line induced motion along the cylinder. The current induces a normal drag on the cylinder which may be determined from a plot of drag proportionality C_D/C_{D∞} shown in Figure 2 as a function of fineness ratio ℓ/d. Equation (1) gives the form for the drag coefficients C_D and C_{D∞} where the area A_D = dℓ and d is the diameter and ℓ is the length of the cylinder. Typically, C_{D∞} = 1.2 for the nonvibrating cylinder. As to the forces experienced in the heave motion, added mass is one input to the equation, Equation (4). It is shown as a function of fineness ratio and an acceleration modulus in Figure 3, from Reference 6. The added mass is given as a ratio to the mass of the displaced water

$$m_d = \frac{\pi}{4} \rho d^2 \ell \tag{9}$$

Figure 2 - Drag Coefficients on Cylindrical Bodies in Normal Flow

Figure 3 - Added Mass on Circular Cylinders in Axial Motion as a Function of Fineness Ratio l/d and Acceleration Modulus U^2/ad

The acceleration modulus is defined as U^2/ad where a is the half amplitude of a sinusoidal acceleration. In the absence of data on damping on cylinders in axial motion, damping forces are assumed to be quasi steady functions of the drag computed at any instant of time from

$$D(t) = 1/2\rho z^2(t) \frac{\pi}{4} d^2 C_D. \quad (10)$$

where for a blunt cylinder $C_D = 0.83$.

Except for surface buoy applications, which are treated in a later subsection, the typical component sensors usually are located in intermediate and/or great depths of submergence. As shown in Table 1, the dominant hydrodynamic characteristics for this range of depth are the steady force, added mass, and strumming force. Since the strumming force is not considered important in the case of streamlined bodies, ample data exist on the steady forces and added mass for sensor and array components in deep and intermediate submergence. Only limited data are applicable to the case of shallow submergence where the strumming and wave effects are important.

Basic Shapes for Mooring Lines

Typical shapes for mooring lines include bare, smooth jacketed, and faired cable and chain. The cable includes wire rope and other constructions, such as electromechanical cable.

Of all the shapes considered, the most data are available for rigid circular cylinders which are considered simulations of flexible cables. Adequate data are available on bare cables of circular cross-section. There is a need, however, to determine the hydrodynamic characteristics of chains and fairings. Particularly, the added mass and damping coefficients for chains and fairings are needed for the design and dynamic analysis of moored systems.

Bare cables are often used in mooring and towing applications. The hydrodynamic characteristics of cables are quite different from those of cylinders of infinite length. One reason is that cables are flexible. A long cable may respond to a flow in many different modes of vibration, depending on the tension and flow speed. For example, the drag coefficient of a bare cable in a flow speed of 2 knots may differ from that of a smaller bare cable in a flow speed of 3 knots, even if the Reynolds numbers are the same for both cases. The tension, mass, and length of the cable must be considered in determining the proper drag coefficient for the cable in the flow.

Skop, Griffin and Ramberg (Reference 7) have developed a mathematical model which accounts for the interdependence between tension, mass, and length of cable and drag on the cable. In many cases, the model yields drag coefficients which are too high. For example, on a long cable the vibration induced by vortex shedding does not lock on to one distinct mode. A better fit to sea trial data is obtained if the maximum amplitude distribution in the model is reduced to 15 to 25 percent of its computed value, and this reduced amplitude is used in the remainder of the computations. Average drag coefficients of 1.7 and 1.9 are obtained on bare cable at sea.

Published data are available for other mooring line shapes. See Reference 8.

Various Shapes for Buoys

Buoys are considered to include floating bodies, surface and submerged buoys, and appendages of buoys. As components of moored systems, the buoys experience wave, current, and wind loads. The important hydrodynamic characteristics are the damping, drag, and added mass of the buoys, and the response of buoys in waves. Strumming is not an important factor because the drag and wave forces are larger than the strumming force induced by current.

Data available on basic shapes discussed in the last two sections are general enough to be applied to wide ranges of sizes and shapes of moored array components and mooring lines. By contrast, the data available on buoys apply to specific shapes and sizes of buoys and may not be easily generalized.

As a sample of data on buoys, Figure 4 compares the drag characteristics in smooth water of various buoy shapes and sizes listed in Table 3. Here, for the same buoyancy (payload carrying capability) hemispheres and disks have lower drag than do spheres. As another sample, Figure 5 shows the heave response of a spar buoy whose

characteristics are given in Table 4. See also Reference 9.

$$\text{EQUATION: } F_n = U/\sqrt{gd}$$

Figure 4 - Drag Characteristics of Spheres and Other Shapes at a Vertical Force to Displacement Ratio of 0.75

TABLE 3. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SURFACE FLOATS SHOWN IN FIGURE 4

Model	Diameter		Weight in Air		Displacement		Note
	in.	cm	lb	fl	lb	fl	
Sphere A	27.75	70.5	69.1	307	409.1	1820	Aluminum
Sphere B	26.00	66.0	17.5	78	335.3	1492	Rubber
Sphere C	12.00	30.5	14.2	63	32.7	145	Laminated Wood
Ellipsoid	9.50	24.1	17.3	79	32.4	144	Laminated Wood, 19-inch long
Hemisphere	20.60	52.3	10.3	46	75.5	336	Laminated Wood, 9.5-inch high
Disk	18.50	47.0	16.0	71	58.2	259	Laminated Wood, 6-inch high

Figure 5 - Heave Response of Spar Buoy Described in Table 4

TABLE 4. FULL-SCALE CHARACTERISTICS OF SPAR BUOY FOR WAVE RESPONSES SHOWN IN FIGURE 5

Buoy Radius	0.2667 m
Overall Length	5.600 m
Mass	1182 kgm
Draft	5.155 m
Fineness Ratio	19.34
Position of G above Baseline	1.735 m
Position of B above Baseline	2.578 m
BG	0.843 m
Moment of Inertia	0.304

G = Center of gravity B = Center of buoyancy

5. Summary and Conclusions

The hydrodynamic characteristics of moored array components such as buoys, cables, fairings, and sensors are available in published and unpublished literature. These data are presented in tables and figures on basic component shapes, on basic mooring line shapes, and on buoys and are presented in terms of hydrodynamic coefficients, added mass and damping, strumming, and wave force and response of buoys.

For the basic component shapes, there are adequate data for the steady flow forces on the shapes either in the submerged or floating condition. Adequate inertia and damping coefficients also can be found or calculated with existing methods. Inadequate data exist for strumming forces, body responses to strumming excitation, and the effects of interference from appendages, attachments to mooring lines, or other nearby components on the hydrodynamic characteristics of the basic component shapes.

For the basic mooring line shapes, there are adequate data on the drag and strumming forces but inadequate data on the inertia and damping characteristics. In addition, the hydrodynamic data on chains are inadequate. It should be noted that the data for cables are either obtained from rigid cylinders or from short cables. The hydrodynamic characteristics of long mooring cables in water are being investigated as parts of ongoing research programs.

For the available buoys, there are adequate data sources for the flow forces and the inertia and damping coefficients. Data are inadequate on the effects of appendages on the hydrodynamic characteristics of buoys.

A systematic evaluation of the literature on basic shapes of moored array components indicates a lack of data on the effects of vibration on their hydrodynamic characteristics. A component, being a part of a moored system, is always in a state of motion. As a result, the flow forces of drag and lift, and the inertia coefficients on a vibrating body are different from those on a body stationary in the flow. An experimental program is needed to evaluate the effects of vibration on the hydrodynamic characteristics of streamlined bodies.

The effect of the length of a flexible cable on the hydrodynamic characteristics of cables and cable fairings is not fully resolved. Analytical and experimental studies are necessary to investigate the responses of moored systems to various environmental conditions.

The effects of the interference of other components on the hydrodynamic characteristics of moored array components are not yet known. An experimental program is suggested to study these effects.

References

1. Morgan, W. B., "Testing of Hydrofoils and Propellers for Fully Cavitating or Ventilated Operation," 11th International Towing Tank Conference, 1966.
2. Berteaux, H. O., BUOY ENGINEERING, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1976.
3. Albertson, N. D., "A Survey of Techniques for the Analysis and Design of Submerged Mooring Systems," U.S. Naval Civil Engineering Laboratory, Technical Report R-815, August 1974.
4. Dillon, D. B., "An Inventory of Current Mathematical Models of Scientific Data-Gathering Moors," Hydrospace-Challenger, Inc., Report TR 4450 0001, February 1973.
5. Berteaux, H. O. and N. K. Chhabra, "Computer Programs for the Static Analysis of Single Point Moored Surface and Subsurface Buoy Systems," Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, Technical Report WHOI-73-22, March 1973.
6. Holler, R., "Hydrodynamic Effect of Harmonic Acceleration," Naval Air Development Center Report AESMTM-29-71, 1971.
7. Skop, R. A., O. M. Griffin and S. E. Ramberg, "Seacon II Strumming Predictions," Naval Research Laboratory Memorandum Report 3383, October 1976.
8. Folb, R., "Experimental Determination of Hydrodynamic Loading for Ten Cable Fairing Models," David W. Taylor Naval Ship Research and Development Center, Report 4610, November 1975.
9. Dern, J. C., "Unstable Motion of a Spar Buoy," 9th Symposium of Naval Hydrodynamics, ONR, 1972.